

Tips and policies for working on Salicaceae nomenclature and taxonomy in Rhakhis

Campbell O. Webb and Quentin Cronk

April 15, 2025

(*Salix* will be used as the exemplar genus in what follows)

See also the main Rhakhis [handbook](#). Feel free to use the [sandbox](#) (Staging Server) to fully explore the system, including creating dummy names. All changes in the sandbox are overwritten daily.

Nomenclatural elements of the data are in gray borders, while taxonomic elements are in orange borders. The following notes cover the former first.

Author String

Abbreviations should use Brummitt & Powell, Authors of Plant Names (1992). IPNI can be used to search for the correct abbreviation. See the [IPNI FAQs](#) for more information.

Publication (Citation)

Imported from IPNI and should be correct. Optimal form: {Abbreviated journal or book name} SPACE {(optional) {Volume} COLON SPACE} {Page} PERIOD SPACE OPEN-PARENTHESIS {Year of publication} CLOSE-PARENTHESIS. See 'IPNI Notifier' below. See the [IPNI FAQs](#) for more information.

Autonyms lack both Author Strings and Citation strings.

Nomenclatural References

Most of these should already be populated with literature and people. At a minimum there should be a link to the protologue. If one has the details of the protologue, but cannot find a URL for an online document, create a Wikidata entry. If one has a PDF of the protologue, upload the PDF to Zenodo and use that DOI as the link.

Autonyms should have a link to the publication of the name that created the autonym.

Type specimens

It is desirable that a link to an online representation of a type specimen is provided for all accepted names, and for all basionyms. The kind of type should be specified in the comments field of the link.

Nomenclatural Status

In order to switch the nomenclatural status of a name from ‘unknown’ to ‘valid’ or another option one **must** actively research the name. However, considering the time required to perform this research for the many names that need to be reviewed, it is only required to check the status for names that are *accepted* and that are currently in an ‘unknown’ state.

Note that before adding a synonym to an accepted taxon, the status of the accepted name must be ‘valid’ (or possibly ‘conserved’).

Homotypic names

This box is computed by Rhakhis. The only option is to add or remove a basionym. If a basionym is specified, all other names that share that basionym are also listed.

Placement

This is the main tool for assigning a taxonomic status. New names, and many existing *Salix* names, are unplaced (anywhere in the WFO taxonomy), denoted by the gray bar above the name.

To accept a name, first the nomenclatural status must be either ‘valid’ or ‘conserved’. The option will appear in the placement dropdown to ‘Raise to accepted taxon within...’, and *Salix* (or a *Salix* species) can then be chosen. The bar above the name will change to orange (i.e., now a taxonomic entity, not just a nomenclatural entity).

To make a name into a synonym of an accepted name, use the ‘Sink into synonymy with...’ option. This is allowed even if the name’s nomenclatural status remains ‘unknown’ (see above).

To move the accepted taxon from one name to its current synonym, first raise the synonym to an accepted taxon with *Salix*, then sink the currently accepted name into synonymy.

Do not move an unplaced infraspecific name into synonymy with a species based solely on sharing a specific epithet with that species. Some taxonomic knowledge or research is needed.

Taxonomic Sources

Should be interpreted as taxonomic placement “according to...”

Every accepted and synonymous *Salix* name should have at least one entry in this list, *unless* the decision to place a name is a new one in which case the Wikidata URL of the person(s) making this decision should be used as the source ([Quentin](#), [Cam](#)). It is unlikely will be making many new decisions about accepted taxa, but we may need to make new decisions about obscure, unplaced synonyms. A full discussion of a new decision is required in the Comments section.

The accepted name should not have a source for each of its synonyms; each of the synonyms should have its own “according to” source.

The earliest published statement by an author about the taxonomic placement of a name should be used as the primary entry, with subsequent (flora, etc.) statements added if time allows.

Where various authorities agree, several entries should be made. Where authorities disagree, the link to the disagreeing authority should be in the Other Treatments field, not here.

If the decision to accept is the same as the protologue in Nomenclatural Source, that entry should be added to the Taxonomic Source as well.

Common (type = Literature) options will be:

- **Flora of North America** Display text: “Argus, G.W., et al. (2010) Salicaceae. Flora of North America 7: 23-162.” URL: link to the online flora page, e.g. http://floranorthamerica.org/Salix_alaxensis.
- **Argus 1973** Display text: “Argus, G. W. (1973) The Genus Salix in Alaska and the Yukon. No. 2 in Publications in Botany. National Museums of Canada, Ottawa.” URL: https://accs.uaa.alaska.edu/wp-content/uploads/Salix_Alaska_Yukon_1973.pdf
- **Dorn 2010** Display text: “Dorn, R.D. 2010, The Genus Salix in North America North of Mexico” URL: <https://www.lulu.com/shop/robert-dorn/the-genus-salix-in-north-america-north-of-mexico/ebook/product-6517733.html>
- **Robert Dorn (in litt.)** Display text: “Robert Dorn (in litt.)” URL: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2894282> Comments: “Robert Dorn’s review of N. American Salix communicated to Quentin Cronk and Campbell Webb via email (2024)”

POWO treatments (many originating from Irina Belyaeva) are classed as ‘Database’ entries.

Other treatments

Use this for any other mentions of this taxon, either taxonomic treatments that disagree with the placement chosen by us, or floras that use a name.

Comments

The stand-alone Comments field should be used for clarifying information about the history and taxonomic status of the record, as in the nomenclatural section of a published treatment. This discussion may combine comments on:

- The original use of the name and authors in the protologue (i.e., Nomenclatural References),
- The editors' own choice to accept or reject a particular publication as the source of the taxonomic placement (Taxonomic Sources),
- Disagreement among authors concerning the taxon's placement (disagreeing publications should be in Other Treatments)

Publications should be cited using a 'Smith (2001)' format, and all discussed publications must be listed somewhere on the page.

For autonyms, the text "Autonym created by " may be added.

The mini-discussion should be signed by following it with [XX, 2025-02-20] (where XX is the reviewer initials, e.g., 'QC' or 'CW').

Do not use the Comments field in the 'Add Reference' popup for the above discussion. That reference-specific comment should be used only for some comment about the reference/publication/database itself (e.g., its availability).

Tracking our review status

Rather than maintaining a separate tracking document or database, we can indicate the state of reviewing using one of two strings in the Comments section: [Review in progress, XX, 2025-01-30] or [Review complete, XX, 2025-01-30] where XX is the reviewer initials, e.g., 'QC' or 'CW'. If a record is visited several times before being 'done' the date of the 'Review in progress' should be updated.

IPNI Notifier

IPNI author strings and publication citation strings are imported regularly and *overwrite* the values in Rhakhis. If a change is made to either the author string or citation string, it is vital to notify IPNI to ask them to update their data.

Since changing IPNI records is laborious for us and them, minor variants in the IPNI citation string should be tolerated. Examples include the publication year not in parentheses, or an extra page range added to the treatment page (e.g., '505 (-507)'). True errors should always be corrected.

Template for email to IPNI:

To: ipnifeedback@kew.org
Subject: <IPNI URN>

Dear IPNI editors,

During the course of working on Salicaceae for the World Flora Online, we believe an IPNI entry requires correction:

Name: <Full name>
IPNI URN: <IPNI URN>
Nature of correction: <Author string | Citation>
Existing value: ...
Corrected value: ...
Reason for change: ...
Evidential links: http...

Thank you,

Note that the IPNI records for autonyms appear to have been hidden (as of March 2025), with text "This name is suppressed" when the link opens. This leads to a IPNI Notifier warning, but no action is required.

How to handle conflicting authorities

As WFO editors we are attempting to find a community consensus on accepted names, but without taking too long. Some independent judgment calls will be required, and as long as the reasons for decisions are documented in the Taxonomic Sources field and the Comments field, these decisions can be further discussed and edited. However, where a major conflict exists for a widespread taxon, we should take our time. In the case of North American taxa, this is most likely to occur when Robert Dorn and George Argus disagree, and in the case of taxa that occur on other continents and go by different names there (e.g., *Salix bebbiana*). While we review the evidence, a note should be added to the Comments section indicating the nature of the conflict.